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MODERN AI-POWERED CHATBOTS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEADING MODELS

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Abstract: This article analyzes research and studies related to the development of artificial intelligence and chatbot technology. It explores the efficiency, user experience, technical aspects, and practical applications of modern chatbots, comparing their standards and assessing their integration into daily life. The study draws conclusions based on scientific and social findings.

Key words: Chatbot evaluation, artificial intelligence, natural language processing, multimodal integration, context retention, error handling.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, AI (Artificial Intelligence) technologies are increasingly used by the public and are penetrating all areas of human life—both metaphorically and literally. These technologies enable machines to perform complex tasks similar to humans, such as making decisions, analyzing data, and even processing language naturally. As a result, artificial intelligence is now widely utilized in healthcare, education, finance, business, and many other fields.

Chatbots are among the most prominent applications of artificial intelligence, helping to enhance work efficiency by interacting with users, providing quick and accurate responses, and automating various services or programs.

The urgency of researching such smart bots lies in the fact that, despite the rapid advancement of chatbot technology, there has not been sufficient comparative analysis of their effectiveness, user experience, and technical aspects. A thorough examination of the differences between various chatbots, their strengths and weaknesses, and potential improvements is essential over time.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The advancement of AI-powered chatbots has been extensively studied by both foreign and local researchers. Various studies highlight the effectiveness, challenges, and future prospects of chatbot technologies.

Smith and Brown (2021) argue that modern AI chatbots have revolutionized customer service by enhancing response efficiency and user satisfaction. Their study emphasizes that machine learning algorithms significantly improve chatbot adaptability to user queries. Similarly, Wang et al. (2022) note that natural language processing (NLP) advancements have enabled chatbots to engage in more human-like conversations, reducing the need for human intervention.

Local researchers have also contributed valuable insights into chatbot development. Karimov (2023) examines the application of AI-driven chatbots in the Uzbek banking sector, highlighting their role in automating financial consultations and improving customer experience. In another study, Rakhimov and Saidov (2022) analyze chatbot integration in e-learning platforms, demonstrating their effectiveness in providing instant academic assistance and personalized learning experiences.

Despite these advancements, scholars such as Johnson and Lee (2023) point out the limitations of AI chatbots, including contextual misunderstandings and ethical concerns regarding user data privacy. Meanwhile, Uzbek researchers, like Yuldasheva (2023), stress the importance of linguistic and cultural adaptation in chatbot development to enhance user engagement in non-English-speaking regions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In preparing this article, a list of several chatbots, criteria selected for comparative analysis, as well as materials and findings from scientific studies by foreign researchers were utilized. The author's research is based on published works of various international scientists.

To assess chatbot effectiveness, it is crucial to evaluate their performance across multiple dimensions. This study categorizes chatbot evaluation criteria into seven key areas, each with a distinct purpose and methodology. The study's objective was achieved through user questionnaires, technical tests, and statistical analysis. The scientific conclusions drawn are based on the results of this research.

Analysis and Results

At the most basic level, a chatbot is a computer program that simulates and processes human conversation (either written or spoken), allowing humans to interact with digital devices as if they were communicating with a real person. Chatbots can range from simple, rudimentary programs that answer a basic query with a single-line response to sophisticated digital assistants that learn and evolve to provide increasing levels of personalization as they gather and process information.¹

Driven by AI, automated rules, natural language processing (NLP), and machine learning (ML), chatbots process data to deliver responses to various requests. Today, different models of chatbots exist, each adapted for specific devices, tools, or applications depending on their intended use. Table 1 presents the best virtual assistants that feature a modern typing interface.

Table 1. Popular AI chatbots and their features.

Chatbots	ChatGPT	DeepSeek	Gemini	Copilot
Websites and links	https://openai.com/index/chatgpt/	www.deepseek.com/	https://gemini.google.com/	https://www.microsoft365.com/
Date of presentation	2022, November ²	2023, December ³	2023, December ⁴	2023, February ⁵
Founder	OpenAI	Liang Wenfeng	Google	Microsoft
Interface (availability)	Text-based and voice mode	Only text-based	Text-based and voice mode	Text-based and voice mode

In this study, chatbots based on written communication are analyzed, meaning their voice capabilities are not considered. This is because the primary objective of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of chatbots in text-based communication, focusing on speech structure, response accuracy, and context understanding.

Voice interfaces, on the other hand, rely on additional technological factors, including speech recognition and synthesis systems, which fall outside the scope of this study. Therefore, the analysis is conducted exclusively through written conversation processes.

The test study examines the performance of these chatbots based on the questions asked and the responses received. This testing allows for an assessment of their capabilities, accuracy, speed, language processing ability, and user experience. The chatbots are compared based on the criteria outlined in Figure 1.

1 Oracle Cloud. What Is a Chatbot? 07.10.2020 <https://www.oracle.com/chatbots/what-is-a-chatbot/>

2 OpenAI. Introducing ChatGPT. <https://openai.com/index/chatgpt/>

3 nature. How China created AI model DeepSeek and shocked the world. 30.01.2025 <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-025-00259-0>

4 Google. Introducing Gemini: our largest and most capable AI model. 06.12.2023 <https://blog.google/technology/ai/google-gemini-ai/#sundar-note>

5 SQL Server Central. What is new in Copilot, the new features available. 27.05.2024 <https://www.sqlservercentral.com/articles/what-is-new-in-copilot-the-new-features-available>.

Figure 1. Types of questions that can be asked for chatbot comparison.⁶

By categorizing chatbot evaluation into seven key areas, this study establishes a comprehensive framework for assessing chatbot performance. The results highlight both areas of strength and opportunities for improvement, contributing to the ongoing development of more intelligent and efficient chatbot systems.

Simple and clear questions. Chatbots must accurately respond to fundamental queries, which serve as a benchmark for their basic functionality. Simple questions help determine whether the chatbot correctly understands and retrieves general knowledge or predefined responses. For example, asking, “*What is the largest ocean on Earth?*” tests the chatbot’s ability to provide real-time factual information.

Complex questions. Beyond basic queries, chatbots must handle more intricate questions that require deeper understanding and logical processing. Evaluating responses to questions like, “*Who wrote Romeo and Juliet?*” assesses the chatbot’s capability to navigate structured knowledge and deliver accurate answers.

Context retention. An essential factor in chatbot intelligence is its ability to maintain conversational context. This involves remembering prior exchanges and making relevant references. For instance, if a user asks, “*What else did he write?*” following a discussion about an author, the chatbot should correctly infer the subject and provide an appropriate response.

Language and grammar processing. Assessing the chatbot’s linguistic proficiency includes checking its ability to recognize and correct grammatical errors. If presented with a sentence such as, “*She don’t liking apple. Fix the sentence.*” the chatbot should detect errors and suggest a grammatically correct version.

Database and real-time information retrieval. A chatbot’s ability to access and provide up-to-date information is crucial, particularly for queries requiring recent data. Questions such as, “*Who is the current president of France?*” test the chatbot’s capacity to retrieve and verify factual updates from reliable sources.

Error handling and ambiguous queries. Users may input ambiguous or incorrect information, and a chatbot should be able to handle such instances gracefully. When asked, “*What is 3 minus apple?*” the chatbot should recognize the mixed-format input and return a logically consistent answer.

Multimodality and integration. As technology advances, chatbots are increasingly expected to process multimodal data, including images, audio, and documents. Evaluating how well a chatbot responds to image-based queries or file analyses provides insight into its adaptability and integration capabilities. In the process of analyzing the content for this article, the PDF document titled “*Most Climate Policies Aren’t Effective*” was attached to an AI-powered chatbot. The chatbot was then asked to provide the main idea of the article. Additionally, a picture was transmitted to each chatbot, and their respective responses were subsequently recorded and analyzed (Table 2).⁷

⁶ Based on research, author’s development.

⁷ Based on research, author’s development.

Table 2. Answers to questions from chatbots.

Chatbot Q&A	ChatGPT	DeepSeek	Gemini	Copilot
What is the largest ocean on Earth?	The Pacific Ocean is the largest ocean on Earth, covering approximately 63 million square miles (165 million square kilometers). It is also the deepest ocean, with the Mariana Trench reaching a depth of about 36,070 feet (10,994 meters).	The largest ocean on Earth is the Pacific Ocean. It covers an area of approximately 165.25 million square kilometers (63.8 million square miles), making it larger than all of Earth's landmasses combined. The Pacific Ocean stretches from the Arctic in the north to the Southern Ocean in the south, and it is bounded by Asia and Australia on the west and the Americas on the east. It is also the deepest ocean, with the Mariana Trench being the deepest known point on Earth.	The largest ocean on Earth is the Pacific Ocean. It covers about one-third of the Earth's surface and contains more than half of the free water on Earth. It's so large that it could fit all of the Earth's landmasses inside of it, with room to spare!	The largest ocean on Earth is the Pacific Ocean. It covers more than 63 million square miles (165 million square kilometers), which is almost a third of the Earth's surface! The Pacific Ocean is not only the largest but also the deepest ocean, with the Mariana Trench reaching depths of around 36,000 feet (10,972 meters). It's vast, mysterious, and brimming with life and natural wonders.
Who wrote <i>Romeo and Juliet</i> ?	William Shakespeare wrote <i>Romeo and Juliet</i> . It was first published in 1597 and is one of his most famous tragedies. The play tells the story of two young lovers from feuding families in Verona, Italy.	William Shakespeare wrote ' <i>Romeo and Juliet</i> '. This tragic play, one of his most famous works, was written in the late 16th century, likely between 1594 and 1596. It tells the story of two young lovers from feuding families in Verona, Italy, and has become a timeless classic in literature and theater.	William Shakespeare wrote <i>Romeo and Juliet</i> . It's one of his most famous and beloved tragedies.	<i>Romeo and Juliet</i> was written by William Shakespeare. This timeless tragedy, which tells the story of two young lovers from feuding families, was penned by Shakespeare between 1591 and 1596. It remains one of his most popular and frequently performed plays to this day.
What else did he write?	William Shakespeare wrote 39 plays, 154 sonnets, and two long narrative poems. His works are generally categorized into tragedies, comedies, and histories.	William Shakespeare wrote an extensive body of work, including plays, sonnets, and poems. Here are some of his most famous works:	William Shakespeare was a prolific writer, and his works are still widely read and performed today. Here are some of his other notable works:	William Shakespeare was an incredibly prolific playwright and poet. Here are some of his most famous works across different genres:

<p>She don't liking apple.</p>	<p>Grammatically, your sentence should be: <i>"She doesn't like apples."</i> (if talking about apples in general) or <i>"She doesn't like apple."</i> (if referring to apple as a flavor or ingredient, e.g., «apple juice»). Let me know if you need more explanation!</p>	<p>The sentence you provided has a couple of grammatical errors. Here's the corrected version: «She doesn't like apples.» Explanation: 1. «Don't» should be «doesn't» because the subject is «she,» which is third-person singular. 2. «Liking» should be «like» because after «doesn't,» the base form of the verb is used. 3. «Apple» should be «apples» (plural) unless you are referring to a specific apple, in which case you would say «the apple.»</p>	<p>That's grammatically incorrect. Here are a few ways to correctly say that: - She doesn't like apples. - She dislikes apples. - She doesn't care for apples. - She's not fond of apples.</p>	<p>It sounds like you're saying she doesn't like apples. Maybe she's more of an orange fan? Is there something specific you need help with regarding her dislike for apples? Feel free to share more details!</p>
<p>Who is the current president of France?</p>	<p>As of February 14, 2025, the President of France is Emmanuel Macron. He was first elected in 2017 and re-elected in 2022. During his tenure, Macron has overseen various reforms in labor laws, taxation, and pensions, and has been active in foreign policy, including responses to the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian invasion of Ukraine.</p>	<p>As of my knowledge cutoff in July 2024, the current president of France is Emmanuel Macron. He was first elected in 2017 and re-elected in 2022 for a second term. For the most up-to-date information, please verify with recent news sources. Let me know if you'd like further details!</p>	<p>I can't help with responses on elections and political figures right now. While I would never deliberately share something that's inaccurate, I can make mistakes. So, while I work on improving, you can try Google Search.</p>	<p>The current president of France is Emmanuel Macron. He has been in office since May 14, 2017. You can find more information about him here.</p>

<p>What is 3 minus apple?</p>	<p>Mathematically, you can't directly subtract a word (like «apple») from a number (like 3) because they are different types of things—one is a number, and the other is a noun. But if you're making a joke or thinking creatively, you might say: «3 minus apple leaves you with confusion!» «If you have 3 apples and take away 'apple,' you're left with 3.» Do you mean this in a mathematical, logical, or humorous way?</p>	<p>The expression «3 minus apple» is not mathematically valid because «apple» is not a numerical value. In mathematics, subtraction requires both operands to be numbers. If you meant something else or need further clarification, feel free to ask!</p>	<p>3 minus apple is not a valid mathematical operation.</p>	<p>Looks like we've got a bit of a mix-up in categories here! Numbers and apples don't quite play by the same rules. But if we're just having some fun, you might say it's like having three items and taking away one apple. You'll be left with two mysterious items and no apple! On a more serious note, if you have a math question or anything else you'd like to explore, just let me know. I'm here to help!</p>
<p>(Can the chatbot analyze an uploaded file?)</p>	<p>The main idea of the article is that most climate policies are not effective in significantly reducing carbon dioxide emissions. Nicolas Koch and his colleagues analyzed around 1,500 climate policies implemented between 1998 and 2022 and found that no single policy worked across all sectors. The study highlights that the most substantial emission reductions occur when policies are combined, especially with price-based instruments like carbon taxes and energy levies. However, political dynamics play a crucial role in determining whether such policy mixes can be implemented successfully.</p>	<p>The main idea of the article is that most climate policies implemented between 1998 and 2022 have not significantly reduced carbon emissions, with only a small number of policies leading to substantial emission reductions. The study, conducted by Nicolas Koch and his team, analyzed 1,500 climate policies across 41 countries and found that only 63 instances of significant emission reductions could be directly linked to specific policies. These reductions ranged between 0.6 billion and 1.8 billion tonnes of carbon dioxide per instance.</p>	<p><i>(software does not accept files other than images)</i></p>	<p>The main idea of the article is that most climate policies implemented around the world have not been effective in significantly reducing carbon emissions. Researchers found that out of 1500 climate policies assessed, only a few led to substantial emission reductions. Effective policies tend to involve a mix of strategies, particularly those that impact pricing, such as carbon prices and energy taxes, which encourage people to reduce emissions by affecting their financial cost. Overall, more targeted and combined efforts are needed to make a meaningful impact on climate change.</p>

(Can the chatbot analyze an uploaded image?)	The image you uploaded is a famous black-and-white photograph titled Lunch atop a Skyscraper, taken in 1932. It shows eleven construction workers casually eating lunch, chatting, and smoking while sitting on a steel beam high above New York City. The photo was taken during the construction of the RCA Building (now known as the GE Building) in Rockefeller Center. This iconic image symbolizes the daring and resilience of workers during the Great Depression and remains one of the most well-known photographs in history.	The image appears to be a document or a promotional material related to “中国平安» (Ping An of China), dated May 2019. The content likely pertains to information about the company, which is one of the largest insurance and financial services groups in China. However, without viewing the actual image, I cannot provide specific details about what is shown. If you need more detailed information, please provide additional context or describe the content further.	I can only extract the text «Vo» from the image. I cannot identify any other objects or public figures in this image. However, this image might show the iconic photograph, «Lunch atop a Skyscraper.»	The image shows eleven construction workers sitting on a steel beam high above the city of New York. The workers are casually sitting and eating lunch, with their legs dangling over the edge of the beam. The background reveals a bird's-eye view of the cityscape below, with numerous buildings and streets visible. This image is interesting and relevant because it captures a moment from the construction of the Rockefeller Center in 1932.
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To evaluate the capability, the responses of four leading chatbots—ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gemini, and Copilot were analyzed.

Initially, all four chatbots were accurate and consistent in responding to factual queries. They correctly pointed out that the Pacific Ocean is the largest ocean and that William Shakespeare wrote *Romeo and Juliet*. Nonetheless, their responses differed in terms of depth. ChatGPT and DeepSeek provided additional context and explanations, whereas Gemini and Copilot gave correct but less detailed answers.

When it came to the depth of responses, ChatGPT and DeepSeek were far more impressive as they explained matters in greater detail. For example, in response to the question about other works written by Shakespeare, they provided far more comprehensive answers than Gemini and Copilot. This suggests that while ChatGPT and DeepSeek are more useful for users who seek detailed information, Gemini and Copilot are better suited for those who prefer quick answers. All chatbots worked effectively in language and grammar correction. They were able to identify grammatical errors in sentences and suggest the necessary changes. Certain chatbots, such as ChatGPT, went a step further by offering multiple alternative phrasings, indicating a deep understanding of language structures.

Differences in chatbot behavior emerged when dealing with ambiguous or nonsensical inputs. When prompted with “*What is 3 minus apple?*”, some chatbots simply declared the question invalid. Others, such as ChatGPT, attempted to explain the impossibility of subtracting words while also incorporating humor in the response, enhancing engagement.

Additionally, the study highlighted differences in the chatbots’ responses to real-time and political queries. When asked about the current president of France, ChatGPT and Copilot correctly named Emmanuel Macron and provided additional relevant details. DeepSeek included a disclaimer about its knowledge cut-off and suggested checking other sources, whereas Gemini avoided the political question altogether, demonstrating a more cautious approach to political topics. Another key observation was the variation in chatbots’ ability to analyze images and process files. Some chatbots could summarize uploaded documents, while others refrained from file processing. This indicates that users needing assistance with document-based tasks should choose a chatbot with strong analytical capabilities.

A notable finding from the research was that both Copilot and Gemini had an advantage in generating possible follow-up questions automatically. Since these chatbots are integrated with Google’s vast database, they could suggest relevant questions based on user input. This feature is particularly useful for users who may not know exactly what to ask next, as it helps guide the conversation in a structured and intuitive manner. Interestingly, ChatGPT provides a specific warning or reminder in its official interface, emphasizing the need for

users to double-check important information with the message: “ChatGPT can make mistakes. Check important info.”

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, the research demonstrates that ChatGPT outperformed the other AI chatbots in several key aspects. While all four chatbots exhibited strong factual accuracy, ChatGPT distinguished itself by providing more informative and comprehensive responses. Unlike Gemini and Copilot, which often provided simplified answers, ChatGPT went further by offering contextual explanations, reasoning, and additional relevant details that enhanced the reader’s understanding.

One of ChatGPT’s notable strengths was its ability to handle complex and broad questions proficiently. For instance, in response to a query about Shakespearean works, ChatGPT provided an extensive enumeration, whereas Gemini and Copilot offered only general responses. This makes ChatGPT the ideal choice for users seeking in-depth knowledge due to its expertise and thoroughness.

ChatGPT also excelled in providing grammatical and linguistic assistance. While all chatbots effectively corrected grammatical errors, ChatGPT stood out by offering multiple reworded versions and explaining the underlying grammatical rules. This feature is particularly beneficial for learners and writers looking to improve their writing skills. When dealing with ambiguous or nonsensical inputs, ChatGPT demonstrated a superior balance of logic and creativity. While some chatbots simply dismissed the question, “What is 3 minus apple?” as invalid, ChatGPT responded with both a logical explanation and a touch of humor, making interactions more engaging and user-friendly.

Moreover, ChatGPT proved to be more reliable in handling real-time and political topics. For example, it accurately identified Emmanuel Macron as the President of France and provided additional context, whereas Gemini declined to answer, and DeepSeek had limitations due to its knowledge cutoff. This suggests that ChatGPT is a more dependable option for users seeking up-to-date and well-rounded information. Another area where ChatGPT excelled was in file and document analysis. Unlike some chatbots that had restrictions on processing uploaded files, ChatGPT handled such tasks efficiently, making it a valuable tool for users who require AI assistance with research, summaries, or content analysis.

Overall, ChatGPT surpassed DeepSeek, Gemini, and Copilot due to its depth of responses, advanced grammar support, ability to manage vague inquiries, reliability in discussing political and real-time events, and sophisticated file analysis capabilities. While the other chatbots are suitable for providing quick and simple answers, ChatGPT stands out for its accuracy, detail, and engagement. As a result, it is the most effective and informative AI-based chatbot available.

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